

The Importance of Educational Criteria in the Development of Patriotic Advantages in Young Students

Mirzakarimov Xudaberdi Yusupovich

Teacher, Fergana branch of the Institute for retraining and professional development
of specialists in physical education and sports

Abstract: This article contains information about educational criteria that should be paid attention to when developing patriotic virtues among students and youth, as well as the use of modern methods in the educational process.

Keywords: Education, patriotic education, methods of education, criteria of education, ethnogenesis of education and upbringing.

Introduction.

In the era of globalization and sharp competition taking place in the world, armed conflicts and confrontations, new threats and risks that are taking place in different parts of the world, including our region, are putting urgent tasks in front of us that cannot be delayed. In the last years of many countries of the world, normative foundations are being created for the integration of educational content, the improvement of innovative preparations for the development of patriotic qualities in young people.

Today, many countries are moving more towards the process of patriotic education than before, in order to ensure their solution, especially the constant satisfaction of their youth to the protection of the motherland. In particular, a large number of scientific research works are being carried out on ensuring national and international level security in the scientific research centers of developed countries and institutions responsible for the defense of the country. In our country, too, serious attention is paid to the issue of patriotic education of young people. In particular, the formation of skills for the application of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process of students studying in the direction of military education up to the call, the delivery of highly qualified professional personnel, was determined as a priority task of improving the quality of Education.

Literature analysis

Military patriotic education a number of specialists in our country have received scientific research work on the issues of developing a positive attitude towards military service and patriotism in young people, mastering military professions. In particular, the education of students and young people studying in the "Timurbek schools" on the basis of historical approaches to patriotic education Sh.M.Mirzakhmedov, the role of upbringing in the formation of patriotic feelings of young people S.A.Akhatov, issues of the importance of methods of education in the patriotic education of students A.Sotvoldiyev, the importance of national action games in the development of patriotic concepts in student youth S.X. Khabibullayev, patriotic education in general secondary educational institutions Sh.Ubaydullayev, methodological

features of the patriotic education of students and social peculiarities of patriotic education Sh.X.Tilavoldiev, national issues of patriotic education U.Z.Melikuzievs it was embodied in the prohibitions carried out.

Military patriotic education in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent states in improving the military pedagogical process in units and ships of the army and fleet in young people studied under A.V. Baraban, V.I. Vdovyuk, N.F. Fedenko, N.I. Kiryashov, V.N. Gerasimov and et al.

In foreign countries, the issues of manifestation as specific forms of education of young people in the spirit of military-patriotism were studied by V.F. Shatalov, E.N.Ilyin, N.N.Paltyshev, V. Ya.Slepov, S. M. Kirov, A. V. Kozlov.

Research methodology in the formation of patriotic qualities in students and young people, in the educational process, along with traditional methods, it is also necessary to apply modern methods of education, which embody national characteristics. While working on the ethnogenesis of upbringing in this process requires each teacher and mentor to acquire scientific knowledge about education and upbringing.

Analyzes and results

The importance of upbringing in the fact that a person matures as a mature, harmonious person on all sides cannot be compared with anything. Upbringing is defined in the scientific literature as follows: “a practical pedagogical process aimed at the formation of certain physical, mental, moral, spiritual qualities in a person; the sum of measures taken in order to ensure that a person has the characteristics necessary for his survival in society.”

Upbringing is the most ancient and eternal value that ensures human humanity. Without upbringing, neither a separate person nor a personality society can exist. Because the values that ensure the existence of the individual and society pass from one generation to another due to upbringing. Upbringing is of decisive importance in the life of any society and any country. Not sufficiently engaged in the upbringing of the younger generation, in general, members of society, the country is doomed to stagnation and crisis. Because the next day of the state and society will be in the hands of this generation. The Hittite of the enlightened scholar Abdullah Avlani, “discipline is for us either life or salvation or destruction or happiness or disaster”, has not lost its significance even today, but, as it is said for the moment, we think that this book does not lose its importance even for future generations. In the formation of spiritual and moral skills necessary for a person to live in a genuine sense, in society, in nature, in the existence that surrounds him in general, a number of types of upbringing are used.

Upbringing is directed based on the importance of its types in their mutual continuity, complementarity and increasing their effectiveness. In the comprehensive education of the individual, through the use of such types of education as moral, aesthetic, labor, legal, civil, environmental, physical education, their impressive value, the qualities inherent in a person are used in the composition. There is another type of upbringing-that it is a patriotic upbringing. Through this type of upbringing, a strong sense of confidence is formed in the love of a person, his own people, his homeland, in the valor of his honor, freedom, in the power of his native power, in his future. As long as a person has a sense of patriotism, he fights for his own solution and for the sake of his homeland, his freedom, the name of or, tries to develop the state in which he lives, fights against shortcomings and injustices, shows loyalty to his homeland. Today, in the context of cybersecurity, the issue of education is becoming even more relevant. A special approach to a number of methods of upbringing, which were used in the process of upbringing, is always required. When it comes to methods in the educational process of patriotic education, they are divided into 3 main groups. Methods concretize in methodology. The methodology is a means of collecting and sorting evidential materials, a specific type of activity. While it differs from methodological principles, it is based on them. These are: the formation of social

consciousness; example-pattern; stimulation and punishment-methods. And the methodology is the sum of methods, methods of doing, carrying out, fulfilling something.

In achieving success in the process of upbringing, in the effective use of its methods, it is necessary to pay special attention to the personality characteristics, temperament and character traits, as well as the ethnic group to which the person belongs, factors that are important in the evolutionary development of the nation. That is, it is necessary to rely on the ethnogenesis of upbringing. Upbringing standards play an important role in this. The concepts of patriotism and military-patriotism arose and developed on the basis of harmonious roots, but are measured on the basis of some issues norms.

Today, patriotic education in a broad sense is manifested in the fact that the nationality, faith, gender and age of members of society, regardless of profession, sincerely fulfill their duties, obligations to the state and society in the interests of the state and people in which they live, responsibly approach their activities in the field, which is due to their professional, civil, sense of inviolability. As the norms of patriotic education, the following are understood:

- the person is able to realize his civic duty and actively participate in social, economic and political processes in society, as well as promote his civic position;
- the presence of a sense of genius. (In the family, in study and labor activities, in the state, in society);
- his own solution and loyalty to his state;
- adherence to the generally recognized national-moral norms in society;
- strict adherence to laws and procedures established in society; - show respect and reverence for the traditions of their ancestors;
- the realization of his place and role in society.

Patriotism refers not only to the humiliation of his state and people from external and internal enemies, but also to such tasks as the stability, peace of the state and society through his study and labor activities, behavior and morality, spiritual image, profession and craft, as well as contributing to its development. Patriotism is manifested in the fact that all members of society are united around a single goal in the development of the state by all sides. That is, patriotism is understood as the Union of all nationalities and elates living in Uzbekistan around a single goal, and not just representatives of a certain nationality or faith. That is why at international sports competitions, at the ceremony of awarding winners of competitions, the flag of the same state is raised and the anthem is sounded. It is not for nothing that, no matter what nationality the winning participant belongs to, no matter what religion he professes, he is considered and assessed as a representative of the child of that country, of that state, of the ring.

Hence the concept of patriotism it is composed of concepts such as protecting the dignity, honor of the land in which he lives, respecting his dream desires, the ideological views that he is promoting, ensuring peace and harmony, serving his development. While the concept of military patriotism:

- interest in military service and love for the military profession;
- deep understanding of his duty and duty as a soldier;
- compliance with the requirements of universal statutes in relations;
- to serve with patience and endurance in the path of the state's madness, its sovereignty, power and peace;
- excellent study of the secrets of the military profession, relentless development of his military skills and knowledge (military-technical, spiritual-spiritual, physical);
- being able to keep state and military secrets;

- diligently carry out your task and duty;
- preservation of self-attached weapons and techniques;
- infinite hatred of the enemy;
- love for his own solution and Homeland;
- the struggle of oneself, the state and the ring to the last moment in defense of the name and peace, and the difficulties faced along this path are expressed by such standards as perseverance and perseverance, and loyalty to one's oath.

Our ring has long respected, glorified and not forgotten the courage, heroism of its brave, brave and patriotic children. Their courage and heroism passed from ancestors to generations and, on the basis of such samples, brought up the younger generation, set an example in upbringing. That is why our ring has long been defined as an or-inappropriate and proud ring.

Conclusion.

To increase the effectiveness of the development of patriotic qualities in students on the basis of an innovative approach, to include in the didactic conditions the stage of educational technologies associated with the formation of a special motivational preparation for the educational process in students.

References:

1. R.Mavlonova va boshqalar. Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi. T.: “Fan va texnologiyalar” 2010 yil.
2. A.Minovarov. Pedagogika. T.: “O‘qituvchi” 1996 yil.
3. Sh.Tilavoldiyev, A.Akbarov. Harbiy vatanparvarlik tarbiyasi asoslari. Farg’ona. 2003 yil 1. R.Mavlonova va boshqalar. Pedagogika nazariyasi va tarixi. T.: “Fan va texnologiyalar” 2010 yil.
4. Sh.Tilavoldiyev, A.Akbarov. Harbiy vatanparvarlik tarbiyasi asoslari. Farg’ona 2003 yil.
5. З.Г.Нуриддинов. Педагогические идеи Абу Райхана Беруни. - Ташкент: Фан, 1989 год.
6. М.Г.Тайчинов. Воспитание и самовоспитание школьников -М.: Просвещение. 1982 год.
7. N.Ortiqov. Ma’naviyat: milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlar. –Toshkent, 1997 yil.
8. G.K.Masharipova. Xorazm Ma’mun akademiyasi allomalari tabiiy-ilmiiy, ijtimoiy-falsafiy va ma’naviy me’rosining ijtimoiy tafakkur taraqqiyotiga ta’siri. Monografiya. – Toshkent: Navro’z, 2019 yil.
9. O.Musurmonova. Talabalarning ma’naviy madaniyatini shakllantirish. – Toshkent: Fan, 1993 yil.
10. N.E.Muhammadiev. Ichki ishlar idoralari xodimlarining kasb etikasi va estetik madaniyati. - Toshkent, 2005 yil.